

Algorithms, Autonomy, and Agency: The Social Practice of Live-Coded Electronic Dance Music

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ABSTRACT

The emergent field of live-coded algorithmic dance music, or *algorave*, challenges orthodoxies about the social mediation of music. Algorave cannot be understood in strictly social-constructivist terms, since the materiality of algorithms and programming code is central to its practice. Nor can a rigidly technological-determinist approach account for the vibrant community of artists and amateurs who make algorave possible by developing coding platforms, teaching programming workshops, moderating online forums, performing, listening, and dancing. Drawing upon actor-network theory, I argue that algorave is best understood as an association between human and non-human agents. The musical potential of algorithms has inspired artists to create coding frameworks, which in turn has made algorithmic composition and improvisation more accessible and facilitated a growing corpus of algorithmic dance music. This perspective forces a critical reevaluation of the social autonomy of musical works. While in theory, algorave music is ultimately reducible to mathematical constructs, in practice it is a networked social activity involving a range of coequal human and non-human actors. The interactions between these actors define not only the sound of live-coded algorithmic dance music, but its emergence as distinct mode of sociocultural production.

1. INTRODUCTION

On the evening of October 16, 2020, two dozen audience members sit, masked and socially-distanced, on folding chairs in the great hall of the Kelham Island Museum in the industrial city of Sheffield, England. In-person attendance for the No Bounds festival is strictly limited because of the coronavirus pandemic, and even the musicians keep a healthy distance from the venue. Iris Saldino and Damián Silvani perform from Buenos Aires and Malitzin Cortes from Mexico City. Alex McLean is the only Sheffield native of the quartet and his presence is felt only virtually.¹

Large projection screens bathe the vaulted ceilings of the former steel mill in magenta light. The show begins with the measured booms of EDM bass drum samples reverberating throughout the hall. A few seconds later, syncopated drum-machine percussion begins to fill in the sonic space. Layer upon layer is added as the music carves out a restless, tentative groove with each stratum in constant flux, pushing and pulling against the rhythmic inertia of the bass drum and against one another. The invisible musicians quickly weave a sonic tapestry out of silence and for the next forty minutes, the hall is filled with the pulsating, evolving sounds of electronic dance music.

The handful of in-person attendees and global live-stream audience showed up to the opening night of No Bounds 2020 to experience an *algorave*, a live coding event in which programmer-performers create electronic dance music from scratch by writing, running, and editing programming code. Algorave is a portmanteau of “algorithmic rave,” and while safety concerns make the performance resemble a polite chamber recital more than a rave, algorithmic music is on full display.

¹ *No Bounds 2020 Virtual 3D - Mica (Algorave) ft. Alex McLean, Iris Saldino, Munksshr & CNDSD*. No Bounds Festival, October 16, 2020. <https://youtu.be/47BqQKsbSbg>

The video screens are divided into three columns each displaying a text editor, where the performers write and edit the programming code that generates the music, giving audience members full visual access to the compositional process. Saldino starts the performance with a typed comment to the audience: “—hello all!!! so nice to be w u today!!!” As the performance unfolds, additional visual layers appear on the screens—undulating geometric forms, kaleidoscopic effects—but they never obscure the legibility of the constantly-changing text. The four performers’ cursors blink as they navigate through the code. We see hesitation as one member of the quartet assigns the value “200” to an algorithm, and after a moment types “500” instead. Typos cause error messages to appear. We watch them pause and consider their next moves and see the screen blink when a new line of code is triggered to change the musical texture.

In live coding, the processing power of the computer is distilled to its most basic function of carrying out procedures and tasks from information provided to it by the programmer to generate musical material. And that information—the commands, variables, inputs and methods sent to the computer—are fully and freely visible. Transparency of process is not a superficial or stylistic quirk of live coding, but rather a central means by which it exerts its social agency.

Floating above the audience in the center of the hall is a binaural microphone broadcasting a live feed to viewers and listeners around the world. It’s shaped like an artificial human head with microphones for ears, allowing headphone listeners around the world (like myself) to experience as closely as possible the sonic environment of the great hall. This disembodied head, wired for sound and broadcasting over the internet, amidst a small crowd in a former English steel mill listening to four musicians on three different continents make dance music out of mathematical algorithms and programming code is an apt metaphor for the distributed, networked nature of modern musical mediation.

Algorithms—abstract ideas about the structure of music—seem central to this musical assemblage. The performers could be mistaken for disembodied minds who communicate only through the arcane syntax of programming code on a screen. Yet this is not the totality of the social situation of algarave. In the orbit of the algorithm is a vibrant social constellation of artists and amateurs who develop coding platforms, teach programming workshops, moderate online forums, perform, listen, and dance to algorithms embodied in music. McLean has described algarave as “a way to experience something as abstract as algorithmic music with your whole body, with your mind, your feet, and everything in between” (Samson 2019) A cultural analysis of algarave must give equal weight to incorporeal algorithms and the technological tools used to access them as the humans who make the musical practice of algarave possible. This balancing act challenges orthodoxies concerning the social mediation of music and forces a critical reevaluation of the autonomy of musical works.

2. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

The first scholarly writing on algarave is a 2014 paper by Alex McLean and Nick Collins presented at New Interfaces for Musical Expression. They describe algarave as “a current locus of activity where algorithms are explored in alliance with live electronic dance music; frequently they are the means of generating novel dance music on the spot from individual component events, or the manipulation of existing dance music segments.” Algarave differs from other forms of live coding and algorithmic music since its focus is on conditional repetition to create danceable, rhythmic loops, as opposed to stochastic or random processes (Collins and McLean 2014, 355).

Algarave was coined to promote an event presented by the organization noise=noise in London on March 17, 2012. The portmanteau is not trademarked, which has allowed it to spread globally and take on different forms in different contexts while always retaining an emphasis on algorithms, music, and dancing. (Collins and McLean 2014, 355). Collins and McLean include a list of algaraves that had taken place at the time of writing, and this archival project continues at www.algarave.com. The number of live algaraves worldwide has grown exponentially each subsequent year and algarave live-streams on YouTube and Twitch became increasingly prevalent during coronavirus lockdowns in 2020.

2.1. Mini-Languages

The crystallization of *algorave* into a distinct practice is due in part to the development of free and open-source “mini-languages” like *TidalCycles*, *ixi lang*, *Gibber*, *Sonic Pi*, and *Orca* that facilitate EDM-style looping and layering (Collins and McLean, 357). Often built on top of earlier music programming environments like *SuperCollider*, mini-languages feature convenient functions that require a deeper level of technical knowhow to code from scratch in the earlier platforms. Their commands are often expressive and carry semantic meaning outside of a coding environment (e.g., “slow” or “fast” to change the speed of a loop) or feature text-based visual representations of patterns (*ixi lang*, *Orca*). According to Thor Magnusson, mini-languages allow performers to engage more directly with musical patterns, rather than the architecture of the computer (2011, 503). They lower the barrier to entry, allowing artists and amateurs to begin creating and experimenting with musical algorithms quickly. New users have reported being able to create simple tracks after only an hour or so of training (Armitage 2018, 35).

2.2. TidalCycles

TidalCycles was created by Alex McLean, who introduced it in a 2010 paper with Geraint Wiggins at the Sound and Music Computing conference. It constantly evolves as McLean and others add new functionality. Documentation of *TidalCycles* is an ongoing process and a wiki at www.tidalcycles.org is its users manual. *TidalClub* (club.tidalcycles.com) is an active and supportive discussion hub, with separate rooms devoted to development and documentation. Mike Hodnick (a.k.a. Kindohm) has created a series of tutorial videos for new *TidalCycles* users.

TidalCycles is a *pattern language* embedded in the earlier Haskell programming language and runs atop *SuperCollider*. The *TidalCycles* user creates and manipulates patterns that govern when and how sound-events occur. This emphasis on patterns helps create a link between an encoding performer and decoding listener, both creating their own musical experience (McLean and Wiggins 2010, 1). Patterns may be explicitly defined, such as a drum sequence, or they may be sets of rules that change the behavior of a sequence. They may be superimposed on top of one another or nested within other patterns to create complex improvisations that obscure to the listener the component rules governing each sub-pattern.

A characteristic affordance of *TidalCycles* is its dynamic interpretation of rhythmic cycles. Once the performer triggers a pattern, it will loop until it is altered or stopped. Changes to the pattern do not disrupt the continuity of rhythm (McLean and Wiggins 2010, 1). This makes it well-suited to the creation of dance music with a consistent pulse. A simple *TidalCycles* example using hi-hat (hh), bass drum (bd), and hand clap (cp) sounds shows the relationship between algorithm and code in *algorave* mini-languages:

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$ every 4 (fast 2)
$ every 3 (0.25 <~)
$ sound “[hh*8?, bd(3,8), ~ cp]”
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The bottom line of this example defines the basic rhythmic structure of the pattern and most resembles a traditional sequencer. The notation *hh*8* distributes eight hi-hat notes across the cycle, while *bd(3,8)* generates a *Euclidean* rhythm in the bass drum part by accenting three of the eight hi-hat notes with bass drum hits (Toussaint 2005, 47-56). “~ cp” places hand claps halfway through each cycle. The ? after *hh*8* makes the pattern less predictable by letting the computer decide if each hi-hat note will play or be omitted based on a 50-50 probability. The hi-hat notes maintain their rhythmic position within the loop, but the digital “coin flips” recur with each new cycle, breaking up the regularity by generating different combinations of eighth notes or rests.

The two *every n* blocks introduce transformations every *n* number of cycles. *0.25 <~* rotates the rhythmic pattern backwards in time one quarter of its overall length every three cycles. *fast 2* plays the drum loop twice as fast every fourth cycle. These two conditions are cumulative so that every twelfth cycle, the pattern is both shifted backwards and played at double speed.

2.3. Embodying the Immaterial

While a particular syntax is required to make these instructions executable by the platform, the code itself is simply a means of accessing mental constructs that can be described in natural language: “play this drum pattern,” “introduce some randomness to the hi-hats,” “play it twice as fast every fourth cycle,” etc. The algorithm itself is independent of any particular programming language or implementation. In this sense, algorithms are no different from the thoughts and intentions of other musicians, which, when translated into sound, allow collaborators to improvise and react in real time to one another (Dahlstedt 2018, 4). Live coding platforms like TidalCycles allow artists and audiences alike to interact with abstract, immaterial algorithms by materializing their output into sound waves that can be experienced by the body and sculpted into aesthetic experiences according to the tastes of the performers.

This interplay between abstract algorithms and sound is central to the practice of algorave and sets it apart from other forms of electronic dance music. Algorithms—*a priori* mental configurations—define the musical material in algorave and give it an internal intelligence and logic. Without algorithms there is nothing to hear, no music to dance to. It is impossible to understand algorave without acknowledging their centrality to its practice. Yet simultaneously, algorave is dependent on a community of artists devoted to exploring the musical potential of algorithms and motivated by a desire to experience them corporally as dance music. Algorave would not exist without algorithms, but an engaged community is necessary to appreciate their musical potential. Without the social practice of algorave, algorithms would remain mental constructs, knowable cerebrally but never experienced phenomenologically. It is therefore necessary to investigate both its material and social dimensions and the ways in which these dimensions interact with one another.

3. SOCIO-MUSICOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES

3.1. Constructivist and Materialist Approaches

The material characteristics of algorave music (algorithmically-generated dance music) and its mode of creation (programming code) have allowed for the emergence of a distinct cultural identity, an algorave *scene* that encompasses a range of practices. In-person algoraves bring together audiences who listen collectively, dance, and mingle, and online performances are typically accompanied by a chatroom where viewer-listeners can interact with one another. *Algorave* is a genre label that artists use to cross-promote concerts and parties, and online repositories like www.algorave.com create networks between geographically-disparate fans. Algorave motivates various forms of digital labor, including the creation and maintenance of open-source live-coding tools, the writing of documentation for these platforms, and the production of tutorial videos for new learners. Mini-languages have been used in pedagogical contexts as a way to teach the basics of programming and members of the algorave scene regularly explore the theoretical and technical dimensions of their work in academic journals and conferences.

Attempts to understand the social function of music fall between two extremes. Does a piece of music, song, or genre derive and exert its socio-cultural agency through its formal and aesthetic properties—its rhythms, harmonies, melodies, instrumentation, and the processes by which these elements unfold within a musical work? Or is the power of a musical work *constructed* by socio-cultural forces—its commercial distribution, the tools used in its creation, its historical importance, institutional support, perceived degree of cultural capital, and adherence or opposition to cultural norms? Music’s ephemerality, as well as the technical training needed to analyze the formal construction of musical works has contributed to its elusiveness within cultural studies, according to sociologist Antoine Hennion. That music is a collective practice is apparent, but without tangible artifacts, the dichotomy between internal and external approaches is difficult to reconcile (Hennion 2003, 4).

The fault line between these methodologies has separated the cultural study of music into two divergent schools of thought. Musicology and its subdisciplines of music theory and history have largely taken the former approach, granting musical works agency and self-determination by carefully analyzing the intrinsic grammar of musical language. Critical sociology, on the other hand, has preferred the latter

approach that privileges the social construction of musical works by “the constraints through which artists and amateurs are unknowingly determined, the conventions through which they recognize and create their world,” and explains their formal properties primarily in relation to external forces (Hennion 2003, 2).

3.2. Adorno’s Popular-Serious Binary

The reasons for this disparity are due in part to the paucity of individuals working across disciplines as well as the influence of one prominent scholar whose work *does* straddle both sociology and music history: Theodor Adorno. Trained as a composer in the modernist of his teacher Alban Berg, Adorno brought a rare degree of technical knowledge to his writings on the sociology of music and acknowledged the role that both intrinsic and extrinsic forces play in the social mediation of music.

For Adorno, music can be neatly divided into two distinct spheres: “popular music” and “serious music.” The distinction between these spheres stems directly from the relationship between extrinsic cultural forces and the intrinsic material properties of musical works. Popular music, in Adorno’s taxonomy, is a market commodity, standardized and manufactured through mechanical production. Market forces determine every formal aspect of the popular musical work: its chord progression, its rhythm, the content of its lyrics. Popular works maintain a veneer of individuality, to give the music consumer the impression of freedom of choice, but these brief moments of departure are allowed only within the framework of familiar, stock schemata (Adorno and Simpson 1941, 22).

Ultimately, the material within a popular song has no real agency, it merely reflects the dominant social forces at the time of its creation. In doing so, it strips both the musical artist and listener of any power to use music as a vehicle for self-expression or identity formation (Adorno 2002, 391). To understand popular music, it is only necessary to understand the social forces that determine its formal properties and permeate all popular music in a particular cultural milieu, such that the material of any popular work is essentially interchangeable with any other (Adorno and Simpson 1941, 20).

“Serious music,” for Adorno, is by definition opposed to standardization and thus autonomous from cultural forces. The materials of autonomous music (which, notably, is exemplified by Beethoven, Brahms, Mahler, and Adorno’s Viennese contemporaries Berg, Webern, and Schoenberg) are self-determined and responsible for the cultural power that this music exerts. Understanding “serious” music requires careful analysis of the musical details that constitute the work itself (Adorno and Simpson 1941, 23). This, for Adorno, is the purest social function of music and it is only when it is truly autonomous—defined solely by its material properties—that it can exert cultural agency. Just as dissonance is necessary in tonal music to resolve to consonance, individual works of autonomous, “serious” music are necessarily dissonant against the backdrop of pervasive musical norms (Adorno 2019, 11).

Adorno is unequivocal in his moral stance on popular music: it is “passive and undialectic” and serves only to reinforce societal forces that contribute to alienation and subjugation. Moreover, faux-“serious” music that relies on stock schemata is “bad,” “rigid,” and “mechanical.” (Adorno 2002, 395; Adorno and Simpson 1941, 26). The totalizing quality of Adorno’s theories and his insistence on the social autonomy (and moral superiority) of Germanic classical music have been roundly criticized (Born 2005, 13). Studies by Hennion (2001) and DeNora (1997) have shown that the perceived greatness of many classical composers is as much a function of culture as the composers’ music itself. Adorno’s highbrow conclusions about “serious” art music largely mirror nineteenth-century ideals and are thus less revolutionary in musicology than they are in critical sociology (DeNora 2003). However, his theories regarding the influence on cultural forces on the material of musical works laid the groundwork for social constructivism, which was taken up by later scholars without Adorno’s “popular” versus “serious” music binary.

3.3. Bourdieu’s Social Constructivism

Perhaps no scholar is more closely associated with social constructivism than Pierre Bourdieu, who codified it into a methodology for understanding all cultural production. Bourdieu’s concepts of *field*, *cultural capital*, and *habitus* have been influential in music sociology, where they are used in varying degrees to contextualize and explain musical taste and production (Prior 2011, 122). The *field* is the social

arena in which cultural production plays out between the numerous agents that inhabit it and whose position is determined by varying degrees of social power (Prior 2008, 304). Adorno's critique of popular music stems from its determination by a capitalist economic system and Bourdieu's social constructivism acknowledges the flow of capital as central to social life. But Bourdieu expands beyond strictly economic capital to encompass *cultural capital*, those symbolic and material markers of taste that define class difference. *Habitus* refers to the engrained behaviors and skills of individuals and institutions that derive from differences in class and capital and motivate the behavior of agents in the *field* (Fiske 1992, 31-2).

Bourdieu rarely engaged directly with music, but did view musical taste as a marker of class difference (Prior 2011, 126). In this view, the perceived superiority of "serious" art music stems from its greater degree of cultural capital, rather than the autonomy of its musical material. A strict application of Bourdieu's theories to music analysis requires stripping musical works of their material agency. The harmonies, rhythms, instrumentation, and form of *all* music can be understood as the by-products of agents in the field of cultural production, motivated by *habitus* and class difference. "For Bourdieu, who took the critical intention farthest, it means unmasking the magical role of 'creation.' In this view, culture is only a façade disguising social mechanisms of differentiation, artistic objects being 'only' means to naturalize the social nature of tastes" (Hennion 2003, 2). Within musicology, this "post-aesthetic" turn has marked a shift away from strictly formal analysis in favor of a focus on institutional and cultural influences. It has been influential in the study of popular music, where the material distinctions between genres or artists are often less pronounced but notions of class, elitism, and counterculture are often significant (Prior 2011, 122).

4. ALGORAVE AS ACTOR NETWORK

In many ways, algorave exemplifies Adorno's ideal of "autonomous music," and could be viewed as a counterargument to his "popular" versus "serious" binary by asserting autonomy and materiality in a popular dance music context. All of the musical material in algorave is, after all, ultimately reducible to mathematical constructs and abstract rules independent of individual artists, places, politics, or economics (Haworth 2018, 557). Yet in practice, algorave is a deeply networked locus of musical activity involving a range of coequal actors, including artists, algorithms, programming languages, online communities, music festivals, teachers, and students whose interactions define not only the *sound* of algorave music, but its emergence as a discrete mode of cultural production. Like other technologically-mediated musics such as dub, glitch, and vaporwave, as well as improvisatory practices like jazz, algorave reveals the limits of both unilateral determinism and rigid social constructivism in musical analysis (Prior 2008, 301; Born 2005, 26).

Recent musical-cultural scholarship has challenged methodologies that hinge on essentialist notions of social context. For scholars like Georgina Born, Antoine Hennion, Christopher Haworth, and Tia DeNora, this has involved revisiting Adorno's ideas regarding the agency of "serious" musical objects that were largely ignored by later sociologists who focused on his theories of "popular" music (Born 2005, 12). Content matters in this approach to the social study of music; the material of a musical work or genre helps define the contours of its interaction with all other actors in a field, including music technology, academic institutions, and presenting organizations. It is out of this system of interactions that a musical practice such as algorave can take shape (Hennion 2016, 392; Haworth 2018, 560).

4.1. Mediators and Intermediaries

Much of this recent scholarship is associated with *actor-network theory*, a methodology developed and championed by Bruno Latour, John Law, and Annemarie Mol, among others. In its purest form, actor-network theory rejects an a priori conception of "society," since the effects of social forces are only observable through the actions of actors. Bourdieu's *field* only exists because of the network of actors that exist within it, and any power structures within the *field* arise from the nature of the actors' associations. If the actors stop interacting, the *field* disappears, since there are no outside forces holding it together. Actor networks are therefore in constant flux, and ANT focuses on momentary associations that arise when agents in the network interact (Latour 2005, 29, 35, 65).

When analyzing associations, actor-network theory distinguishes between neutral *intermediaries* and transformative *mediators*. Both relay intention between actors, but an intermediary has no effect on the nature of an association, it merely transports meaning or force to another actor unaltered. Mediators, on the other hand, are interstitial entities that shape social interaction by transforming, distorting, or modifying the meaning of the elements they carry. Whether an entity in a network is a mediator or intermediary is not immediately apparent or stable—passive intermediaries can become active mediators. The transformations caused by mediators can be multiplicitous and have a profound influence on a network of associations (Latour 2005, 39).

4.2. Humans and Non-Humans

One of the more controversial aspects of actor-network theory, yet one of the most important for the study of algorithmic music, is the notion that non-humans have potentially as much agency as humans in defining the nature of associations. Musical algorithms and programming languages are as central to the practice of algorave as the (human) artists who use them (Latour (Johnson) 1988, 310). These non-humans only become significant to a network when they work as mediators that leave a fingerprint on human interactions. In other words, mediating non-humans are not simple surrogates for human agency, but rather potentially coequal agents in the social practice of algorave (Sayes 2014, 138).

Strictly materialist and strictly social-constructivist analyses of algorave break down because both treat certain actors as intermediaries when they are in fact mediators. In the former case, human actors are disenfranchised; algorave artists merely relay the music generated by algorithms and programming code. In the latter, algorithms and programming languages passively reflect the will of the algorave scene. In reality, the social practice of algorave is not unilateral in either direction, but rather results from the two-way exchange that results from the interaction of human and non-human agents (Haworth 2018, 560). The musical potential of algorithms has inspired artists to create coding frameworks, which in turn has made algorithmic composition more accessible and facilitated an ever-growing corpus of algorave music. All of the actors in the algorave network—humans and non-humans—exert their agency upon one another to define the contours of algorave as a distinct musical-social practice.

4.3. Sites of Mediation: Thor Magnusson

Social formations like algorave are inherently volatile and it only in moments of mediation or translation that a network of associations becomes visible. Analyzing a musical practice with an actor-network methodology requires identifying those sites in which the will of agents is transformed through mediation. The conditions by which musical-cultural identity and meaning become clear by tracing the transformative interactions of mediating actors including musical material itself. This is the strategy of Georgina Born and her contemporaries, “If we accept that patterns of meaning projected onto music are routinely stabilized, that they can attain some kind of reproduction or closure over the long term, then it behoves us to ask under what conditions this is so.” When these mediations persist for a span of time—the nine years since the first algorave in London, for instance—a distinct musical practice emerges.

Testimonials by figures in the live coding scene highlight moments of mediation that allow us to trace associations between actors that activate algorave as a social practice. Thor Magnusson (the creator of *ixi lang*) was an experienced user of SuperCollider when he set out to learn a new platform called Impromptu. Magnusson found that the functional and aesthetic differences of the two programming languages as well as the online culture surrounding them influenced his musical thinking. While both allowed Magnusson to compose and experiment with the same algorithms and signal flow, neither was a passive intermediary between composer and music. Magnusson’s work in SuperCollider focused on the synthesis of sounds, whereas in Impromptu, his attention shifted toward more traditional compositional structures like notes, scales, and beats. Both platforms are equally able to handle composition at both micro- and macro-levels but each inspired a different way of approaching music (Magnusson 2011, 6).

Magnusson’s autoethnographic account of learning Impromptu challenges the notion that technology is a neutral intermediary in music creation. Both the practical and artistic differences of the two

programming languages (SuperCollider and Impromptu) as well as their communities of users influenced not only Magnusson's thought process, but the sound of the music he produced (Haworth 2018, 561). Magnusson's experiences with Impromptu also influenced the design of *ixi lang*. In their first paper on *algorave*, The mediating agency that cycle-based coding environments like *ixi lang* and *TidalCycles* has shaped not only the sound of *algorave* music, but the way in which artists think about music production. (Collins and McLean 2014, 357).

4.4. Gender and Community in Algorave

Composer and professor Joanne Armitage, who performs in the "algo-pop" duo ALGOBABEZ recounted her experiences teaching women-only live coding workshops in "Spaces to Fail In: Negotiating Gender, Community, and Technology in Algorave." The first all-women live coding workshop took place at Huddersfield University in 2015. Since then, the number of women in the *algorave* scene has increased considerably (Armitage 2018, 34).

Women are less likely to work in technological fields and gender discrimination in computer work (including in the free and open-source community) has been well-documented (Nafus 2011, 671). Digital music production suffers from many of the same gender inequalities as other tech fields and music producers are more likely to be male, which has influenced the design and marketing of commercial music production software. Commercial platforms typically feature a graphical user interface that encourages a particular mode of music creation (commercial programs are mediators, too) that due to its user base is frequently coded male. The women in Armitage's workshops often felt pressure to master commercial software like Ableton Live before they would be taken seriously (Armitage 2018, 37).

The comparatively direct engagement with musical materials made possible by live coding has allowed *algorave* to be a site of greater gender equality relative to electronic music as a whole. By creating music with code, the workshop participants felt greater freedom to experiment, play, and fail. Several have gone on to become *algorave* artists and perform regularly. Armitage describes *algorave* as reframing the relationship between human and computer, to include a much broader network of different supportive parties (Armitage 2018, 35). The mediation between algorithm and musical material and the emphasis on teaching and learning have disrupted social inequalities and allowed *algorave* to become a venue for more equal musical participation. The transformational engagement with code described by Magnusson affects not only the artist and their music, but resonates throughout a broader network of associations.

5. CONCLUSION

These moments of mediation in *algorave* demonstrate the necessity of networked thinking in understanding the social situation of contemporary music. Social constructivism and material determinism offer clues for understanding the way music works in society, but both fall short when they do not acknowledge the two-way influences that human and non-human actors exert on one another. Live-coded electronic dance music is an exciting new arena that is reframing music production as a networked social practice involving abstract algorithms, concrete technologies, and a community of artists and amateurs devoted to exploring this new direction in music creation.

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